

GETTING STARTED WITH THE RSE MOVEMENT WITHIN YOUR ORGANIZATION: A GUIDE FOR INDIVIDUALS

The US-RSE National Organization Empowerment
Working Group

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Authors:

Rinku Gupta, Argonne National Laboratory, rgupta@anl.gov

Gregory Lemieux, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, glemieux@lbl.gov

Contributors:

Keith Beattie, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, ksbeattie@lbl.gov

Jon Guyer, National Institute of Standards and Technology, guyer@nist.gov

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1. Introduction

Welcome to the guide on initiating the Research Software Engineers (RSE) movement within your organization. If you're an individual passionate about championing the cause of RSEs, your commitment to raising awareness and fostering a sense of belonging is truly commendable. This guide is designed to empower you with proactive steps to ignite positive change, connecting RSEs and amplifying their contributions. Within these pages, you'll discover steps and strategies to establish an initial RSE community, promote essential knowledge sharing, and inspire management to recognize the vital role of RSEs in today's evolving landscape. Your dedication, coupled with these insightful guidelines, puts you on the path to driving impactful change and cultivating a thriving environment for RSEs to flourish. Let's embark on this journey together.

The guide is structured into distinct sections, commencing with the creation of awareness and assessment of interest surrounding the topic of RSEs. It progresses to building an informal RSE community and recruiting allies within your organization, with the ultimate aim of establishing a formal RSE society or affinity group within your organization. The term "affinity group" is used liberally in this document, and it is defined as a set of people linked by a common interest or purpose. While the guide outlines the creation of a formal RSE society/affinity group - one that is recognized by your organization - as an eventual goal for completeness, it is essential to emphasize the significance of the preliminary steps. Fostering RSE awareness, securing allies, and cultivating a sense of community among RSEs are pivotal, even when uncertainties linger about the formation of an eventual affinity group. These initial actions establish the groundwork for an RSE culture, empowering collaboration, support, and advocacy for the indispensable role of RSEs within an organization.

2. Raising Awareness and Assessing Interest

As an individual/group of individuals, you embark on a journey to contribute to the growth and empowerment of RSEs within your organization, it's natural to begin by gauging the existing interest levels. While your passion and enthusiasm is driving you to make a difference, understanding the landscape and the enthusiasm for the RSE cause is a crucial initial step. In this section, we will delve into *practical strategies that allow you to effectively create awareness and assess interest, identifying the most fruitful avenues that offer a substantial return on your time investment*. By strategically focusing on these actions, you can lay a strong foundation for your efforts and set the stage for impactful contributions that resonate with the RSE community.

The term “Research Software Engineering” is fairly new and not broadly known, especially among staff that do not regularly interface with software development at your workplace. Building awareness of the terminology and what makes it distinct from software engineering in other contexts is the first order of business.

When conducting outreach, it is important that you consider your audience and what type of message they may be most receptive to hearing. Some of the individuals may identify as RSEs while others may be supportive of the RSE concept. Some could be key stakeholders capable of providing support for conducting outreach in specific venues tailored to specific audiences. Consequently, the suggestions below are categorized by audience type. The formality of the engagement method may vary from casual to formal within each category. Feel free to pick and choose based on your comfort level and what suits your organization.

Close colleagues

This category consists of people that you know the best in your institution: members of your project or team that you interact with often or perhaps the people you hang out with at lunch or get coffee with regularly. These people are going to be the most easily engaged and likely interested in what you have to share about RSEs given your previous experiences together. As such, this is naturally the first place to start with when assessing the landscape of RSEs in your organization. You will likely find great opportunities and a willing audience to inform people about RSEs in more formal settings as well.

1. **Mentors:** Chances are you have a close colleague or mentor who may have some insights into how your institution has engaged with RSEs or RSE-like concepts in the past. Ask these individuals to share their experience!
2. **Team Presentation:** Start within your own team, sharing insights about RSEs and their potential value. Foster awareness and interest among your immediate colleagues. Depending on the appropriateness of the venue, you may be able to ask for time on the agenda of an existing meeting that you attend to present RSE introductory materials.

Departmental

Colleagues in the departmental category are those with whom you are acquainted, but may not interact with on a regular basis. That said, they are the next most likely audience for your outreach efforts as their physical or subject matter proximity to you and your work role will make it easier for you to find common ground. Even if they are

only exposed to the RSE concept briefly, they will likely feel more comfortable reaching out to you for follow-up based on their familiarity with you.

3. **Informal Conversations:** Initiate casual discussions with colleagues, managers, and team members about RSEs and their role. Try to gauge their familiarity and interest levels through friendly chats.
4. **All Hands Presentations:** Offer to give a brief presentation during all-hands or department meetings, introducing the concept of RSEs and their potential benefits to projects and research.
5. **Engage in Networking:** In addition to industry conferences, attend internal networking events where RSEs and RSE-adjacent concepts might be discussed. Bring back insights and share them with colleagues.

Management/Human resources

Engaging management and human resources to raise awareness about RSE concepts likely has some of the highest potential impact of all the categories here. Finding a strong ally in management can provide your efforts with a sense of mission alignment and other benefits that can come with having the support of those who make decisions on hiring and funding, which will help attract others and smooth out potential bureaucratic bumps in the road. That said, outreach to this group likely requires more formal engagement and as such may be better suited once a larger group of self-identified RSEs have conducted more ground work in raising awareness. Until that time, here are some ways you might engage with management directly:

6. **1-on-1 check in:** It's a good idea to check with your direct management before embarking on more formal initiatives, to ensure that it at least does not conflict with existing goals. This could be done during existing 1-on-1 meetings in which management will purposefully be focused on receiving your feedback and ideas, such as performance evaluations or open-office hours. Highlight how RSE efforts help meet your personal, team, department, or institutional goals.
7. **Volunteer with institutional committees:** There are likely multiple departmental and institution-wide committees and groups that work on a variety of topics to improve life in your organization. Often these will be led by or include participants that are members of management. Showing that you are a committed and reliable member of a large volunteer group can go a long way to building confidence with management, potentially providing you with a more receptive audience at a later date.
8. **Submit questions to town halls/forums:** Management will often hold forums or town halls in which they will solicit questions and feedback from employees. Assuming the venue is appropriate for raising awareness about RSE concepts,

these are good opportunities to not only expose management to these ideas, but also forum attendees.

Institutional

This category is by far the most formal of all the categories. Reaching out to the whole institution necessitates adhering to various standards of conduct and communication requirements. Make sure to do research in this regard, including engaging your direct management (see above). They will very likely be able to provide you with feedback and guidance on what sort of message will be most effective for such a generalized audience.

9. **Internal/Email Surveys:** Create a short, focused survey that asks about RSE awareness and interest. Share it through existing communication channels and encourage participation specifically targeting RSE awareness and potential interest. Surveys stand a better chance when they are supported by some-level of leadership. Remember that too many surveys can be taxing and that they come with some requirements around maintaining confidentiality and security with any personal details.
 10. **Intranet Article:** Write a brief article or blog post about the significance of RSEs and their contributions. Share it on your organization's intranet or relevant communication platforms. Share success stories or case studies of RSE contributions to projects or research endeavors.
 11. **Innovation Showcases:** If your organization holds innovation or showcase events, consider featuring RSE-led projects and their outcomes.
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3. Building an informal RSE community

Having raised awareness about the RSE movement within your organization and found other individuals that identify as such, you will likely want to find ways to connect and strengthen your ties. Building an informal community of fellow RSEs who share your passion and vision can amplify your efforts and drive positive change for everyone. In this section, we'll explore *practical strategies to cultivate your ties within your organizational context*. By fostering connections, engaging in thoughtful conversations, and collaborating across departments, you can create a strong foundation for elevating awareness and understanding of the valuable contributions of RSEs.

Creating space

One of the first things to do when you've found a group of other RSEs is to set up a space in which you can meet and discuss your ideas. In fact, you may find that multiple types of venues are appropriate for different types of engagement within your burgeoning community.

1. **Lunch/Coffee break Chats:** Organize informal brown bag lunches or virtual coffee breaks where RSE-related topics can be discussed in a casual setting. This relaxed setting can encourage open conversations.
2. **Slack Groups:** Create a dedicated Slack channel (or other asynchronous chat application) for RSE discussions, news, and resource sharing. Post regularly to encourage participation and interaction.
3. **Regular RSE Group Reading Session:** Establish a regular reading session where interested individuals gather to discuss and analyze articles, papers, or trends related to the RSE field.
4. **Engage with US-RSE:** Engage with the US-RSE organization as a group on community calls together. This will provide a natural time and incentive in which to meet up and cultivate a sense of connection to the larger community outside your institution.
5. **Set up a shared google drive:** You find yourself wanting to easily share and collaborate on documents together, so starting up with a Google Drive (or other shared digital storage) is a good first step.

Participate Together

Participating in a variety of activities together can help to forge a sense of togetherness beyond your shared goals. It will also help you work better together and will give a sense of your skill sets beyond those you employ as RSEs in your work role. This will allow you all to determine what roles you may be more comfortable in fulfilling if you decide to move forward into more formal and challenging activities as RSEs. The following subheadings include a variety of activity categories.

Learn

6. **Collaborative Skill-Sharing:** Organize skill-sharing sessions where RSEs showcase coding techniques and tools, fostering cross-departmental learning. These could be on simple topics.
7. **Advocate for RSE Training:** Suggest RSE-specific training opportunities to HR or Learning & Development, emphasizing their importance within the

organization. While this may/may not be difficult to achieve, it's a good way to know HR/Training people and have allies among them.

8. **Participate in Interdepartmental Workshops:** Join workshops or seminars from other departments to discuss RSEs and their role in interdisciplinary projects.

Build

9. **Collaborate on Research Proposals:** Offer RSE expertise for research proposals, showcasing their value in project development.
10. **Collaborate on Projects:** Partner with colleagues on a joint project, showcasing how RSE expertise can elevate project outcomes.

Volunteer

11. **Engage in Professional Networks:** Connect with colleagues on professional networks within the organization, discussing RSEs and their benefits.
12. **Support Diversity Initiatives:** Collaborate with diversity groups to emphasize the collaborative and interdisciplinary nature of RSE roles. This will give opportunities to create RSE awareness among DEI folks.
13. **Incorporate RSE Perspectives:** During brainstorming sessions, encourage colleagues to consider RSE perspectives for innovative solutions.

Advocate

14. **Share RSE Success Stories:** Highlight instances where RSE contributions positively impacted research or project outcomes.
15. **Highlight RSE Contributions:** Share RSE-related articles or resources on internal communication platforms to promote awareness. Forward it to your connections and encourage them to share similar highlights.
16. **Nominate RSEs for Recognition:** Nominate (or raise awareness among managers to nominate) exceptional RSEs for recognition or awards within the organization.
17. **Share RSE Webinars or Events:** Invite colleagues to RSE-related webinars, workshops, or presentations to spark interest and engagement.
18. **Attend Interdisciplinary Gatherings:** Participate in interdisciplinary gatherings or forums to introduce RSE concepts to colleagues from various fields.
19. **Advocate for RSE Resources:** Lobby for dedicated resources or support for RSEs, emphasizing their role in advancing research outcomes.
20. **Cross-Departmental Team Presentations:** Deliver short presentations during team meetings, highlighting the role of RSEs in enhancing software development for research.

4. Recruiting RSE Allies

In the journey to raise awareness about the RSE movement within your organization and forming a RSE community, allies play a pivotal role. Here, “allies” are defined as *colleagues* who can help advocate for RSE needs, but may or may not identify as an RSE themselves. In this section, we'll explore *practical strategies to cultivate allies within your organizational context*. Some points in this section may overlap with the sections on *Raising Awareness* or *Building informal RSE communities* above. While the strategies between these sections may share similarities, the goals differ. The focus of this section is to work on strategies for pinpointing a network of specific passionate individuals who can work with you to actively contribute to advancing the RSE mission.

Raising Awareness

Raising RSE awareness is crucial to identifying allies. Identifying allies is essential because these individuals possess the potential to significantly influence and champion the cause, contributing diverse perspectives and collaborative efforts. By recognizing specific allies, you not only bolster the impact of your advocacy but also foster a collective momentum toward a shared objective. Some ideas for identifying specific allies through raising awareness are:

1. **Informal Discussions:** Similar to the section on “Creating Awareness and Assessing Interest”, engaging colleagues from various teams in conversations about RSE roles in their teams and their contributions within the organization is a great step towards identifying and building allies.
2. **Cross-Departmental Coffee Chats/Lunchtime Learning Sessions:** Arrange lunch/coffee meetings with colleagues from different departments to discuss RSEs and their impact on research and projects.
3. **Cross-Departmental Team Presentations:** Deliver short presentations during team meetings, highlighting the role of RSEs in enhancing software development for research.
4. **Engage in Research Conversations:** Participate in departmental meetings where research projects are discussed, contributing RSE insights.

Recognizing RSEs

As new allies are identified, it becomes crucial to initiate small joint tasks, fostering a sense of involvement and appreciation that encourages them to seek additional allies. A key aspect of this collaborative effort involves working together to recognize the invaluable contributions of RSEs within the organization. This recognition not only

emphasizes the impact of RSEs but also strategically contributes to the ongoing recruitment of new allies. Actively acknowledging and promoting the achievements of RSEs establishes a foundation for garnering future support from emerging colleagues.

5. **Highlight RSE Contributions:** Empowering identified allies to share RSE-related articles or resources on internal communication platforms involves them in the process and promotes awareness throughout the organization. Encouraging the forwarding of such articles to their connections fosters a ripple effect that aids in recruiting new allies.
6. **Nominate RSEs for Recognition:** Collaborating with allies to nominate exceptional RSEs within their sphere of influence for recognition or awards within the organization acknowledges the outstanding work of RSEs and actively involves allies in the recognition process.
7. **Share RSE Success Stories:** Working closely with allies to highlight instances where RSE contributions have significantly impacted research or project outcomes involves allies in actively promoting RSE successes. This collaborative storytelling approach showcases the value of RSEs.

Inviting people in

To recruit fresh allies, it's effective for you and your existing allies to invite individuals who may not initially identify as RSEs to participate in RSE-run events. Working closely with existing allies to promote and incorporate some of the below strategies, especially in educating those interested, becomes a compelling approach to showcase the impactful work of RSEs and expand the network of supportive allies.

8. **Share RSE Webinars or Events:** Invite colleagues to RSE-related webinars, workshops, or presentations to spark interest and engagement.
9. **Collaborate on Projects:** Partner with colleagues on a joint project, showcasing how RSE expertise can elevate project outcomes.
10. **Collaborative Skill-Sharing:** Organize skill-sharing sessions where RSEs showcase coding techniques and tools, fostering cross-departmental learning. These could be on simple topics.

Showing up

Being an earnest and active member of your workplace community will go a long way to forming strong bonds. Seeing RSEs pitching in as a group in other non-RSE focused events is a great way to find new allies, and maybe even find another passion of your own to support!

11. **Participate in Interdepartmental Workshops:** Join and ask existing allies to join workshops or seminars from other departments to discuss RSEs and their role in interdisciplinary projects.
 12. **Incorporate RSE Perspectives:** During brainstorming sessions, encourage colleagues to consider RSE perspectives for innovative solutions.
 13. **Engage in Professional Networks:** Connect with colleagues on professional networks within the organization, discussing RSEs and their benefits.
 14. **Support Diversity Initiatives:** Collaborate with diversity groups to emphasize the collaborative and interdisciplinary nature of RSE roles. This may provide opportunities to create RSE awareness among DEI folks.
 15. **Attend Interdisciplinary Gatherings:** Participate in interdisciplinary gatherings or forums to introduce RSE concepts to colleagues from various fields.
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5. Starting a formal RSE Affinity group

Getting Started

So, you've got the spark—you and your allies want to kick off an RSE affinity group at your workplace, that is perhaps recognized as a more “formal” entity compared to the initial informal community that you have tried to establish, as outlined in the previous sections. As a reminder, in the [Introduction](#) we defined an affinity group as a set of people linked by a common interest or purpose (if you are inclined, you can also use another term such as RSE society, RSE club, RSE community, RSE network, RSE circle, RSE hub, RSE chapter etc., in lieu of the RSE affinity group). You've done the groundwork, Research Software and connecting with fellow RSE. Perhaps you've even found a handful of allies who are generally on board with the concept. The initial excitement is there, but what comes next in turning this idea into a tangible formal reality?

Research and Preparation: Laying the Foundation for Success

To establish a strong foundation for your RSE affinity group, it is essential to undertake a thorough research and preparation phase. Begin by investigating existing RSE organizations, such as US-RSE. Understanding their mission, goals, and values serves as an excellent starting point. Ideally, your objective may be to initiate an RSE chapter or affinity group affiliated with a national-level organization like US-RSE. However, as of December 2023, US-RSE does not currently support the creation of local chapters or

affinity groups. It's crucial to be aware of this limitation, although it may change in the future as US-RSE expands. Future versions of this document should be updated to reflect any developments in this regard.

Next, explore whether there are existing RSE affinity community groups at institutions similar to yours. Other institutions may have formal or informal RSE groups; such groups may go by the names of societies or forums, etc. Many organizations have formally funded RSE research groups/teams as well. These funded RSE research groups/teams have roles and responsibilities that differ from those of RSE affinity community groups. Network with individuals in these RSE groups to glean insights into the processes they've followed, the differences in their operations, and the experiences they've had. Learning from their journeys can provide valuable perspectives, potentially saving you from potential pitfalls and illuminating best practices. This preparatory phase sets the stage for a well-informed and strategic approach as you navigate the exciting path of establishing and growing your RSE affinity group.

Viability assessment

Active Members: Building a Collaborative Team

Do you have a substantial group of colleagues who identify as RSEs and share an interest in collaborative organizing? Are there enough individuals willing and able to meet regularly and volunteer for specific tasks? If your group is relatively small, there's a risk of high burnout unless you keep your list of affinity group tasks manageable and actively work to expand the number of volunteers involved. Balancing the workload and fostering a collaborative spirit among a sufficient number of members is crucial for the sustained energy and effectiveness of your RSE affinity group.

Allies: Gauging Supportive Networks

Have you assessed how open those around you are to the concept of RSEs and RSE affinity groups? Are there supervisors who are already aware of and supportive of your endeavors? Although not a make-or-break factor in the initial stages of launching an affinity group, having insight into the general receptiveness of your surroundings is beneficial. Understanding potential challenges and identifying supportive figures early on can prove instrumental when seeking recognition for your RSE affinity group. This foresight helps in building a network of allies who can provide assistance and advocacy as you progress with your affinity group initiatives.

Affinity-Group Vision

Undoubtedly, you harbor a vision for RSEs like yourself within your workplace—a vision that calls for formal acknowledgment of your activities to propel you and your colleagues towards that common goal. That said, based on the amount of volunteer labor you can invest into your new affinity group, what can you reasonably expect to accomplish in the short term? Sketching out a set of definable goals that point in the direction of your affinity group's overall vision, however amorphous that vision may be, is a good exercise to help gauge the scope of the work that lies ahead. Be pragmatic about the amount of volunteer labor available and focus on setting a single, concrete goal for the inaugural year. This approach ensures a realistic and impactful start, laying the foundation for the steady evolution of your RSE affinity group.

Establishing an Affinity Group

You and your colleagues feel that you have a viable plan for starting out with your new organization and are ready to solicit formal recognition. This means applying for recognition from your workplace. The purpose of seeking formal recognition is to provide your affinity group with a variety of resources to help attain its stated goals and a sense of legitimacy from your peers. Doing so will likely provide an easier path for working within your institutions to promote and advocate for RSEs.

Gaining recognition by your institution will depend to a large degree on how it recognizes and supports other professional advocacy groups. You may be familiar with how this works based on other professional organizations that you may be a part of. If not, try surveying your colleagues to see if they are members of any organizations that have affinity group affiliations within your institution. Assuming support for professional organizations exists, you will likely find that a formal recognition process will be readily available.

If such a support structure does not exist for professional organizations, you may find that there are other interest groups that are supported that fall under non-professional activities, such as language practice groups, fitness groups, etc. Toastmasters groups are an example of an educational interest group that can commonly be found in many industries. It may be possible to gain recognition for your affinity group through the same structure. If no formal recognition pathway exists, you may find it unnecessary to solicit formal recognition as long as your activities are within the permissible bounds of your institution's rules. Please make sure to consult with your management if you have any questions so as to not run afoul of your institution's rules.

Affinity-Group Organization

There are many, many ways to organize an affinity group with varying degrees of formality, levels of authority, defined roles of responsibility, etc. That said, it is very likely that the shape of the affinity group will change over time to best suit its needs and based on the scale of the current membership. While smaller, new affinity groups may find it easiest to coordinate and conduct tasks in an ad-hoc manner, it is likely that some sort of structure will be necessary to facilitate planning as affinity groups grow. As such, do not be afraid to try different ways of organizing and learn lessons as your affinity group grows!

Affinity-Group mission

The purpose of a mission statement is to provide affinity group members, potential or active, with a clear statement about what your affinity group seeks to affect at your institution. Your affinity group's mission will align with and expand upon the vision you identified at the start of this process. The statement should be concise so as to be easy to digest. It should be broad enough to still be recognizable to your affinity group over time, i.e. it should not consist of concrete measurable goals that have a definitive end date. Conversely, the mission should be specific enough to delineate your affinity group from other professional organizations that might have goals in common due to overlapping interests. This way potential members can better understand which organization best aligns with their interests and conveys what they likely can expect when participating with your group.

Affinity-Group management

The way in which your affinity group's management is structured may be well defined by the requirements for recognition from your institution. Institutions are typically centered around projects with multiple contributors working towards a common goal and working in these institutions means many of you will be well poised to help define how your affinity group manages the tasks it needs to accomplish its goals. This involves setting up and conducting regular meetings, instituting and maintaining repositories of official documentation, developing materials to communicate internally and externally, etc. Take advantage of the areas of commonality that you and fellow members have in how the projects you work on are organized and experiment with different methods where you find areas of difference.

Establishment and Growth strategies

Once a RSE affinity group is established within an organization, the next immediate steps naturally pivot on the specific context of the organization/institution and the

nuances of its management structure. Recognizing the inherent diversity in organizational dynamics, this guide refrains from prescribing stringent sequential next points to the affinity group organizers. Instead, the RSE affinity groups' leadership should tailor their approach according to what aligns best with the unique characteristics of their organization. Being adaptable will allow organizers to determine the most effective strategies for fostering engagement, collaboration, and impact within their specific organizational framework. Whether it involves initiating internal communications, coordinating with management for support, or tailoring activities to suit the preferences of the RSE community, the organizers have to decide the immediate steps that align with the needs and culture of their organization. This is necessary so that the establishment and growth of the RSE affinity group are organically integrated into the fabric of the organization, fostering a sustainable and impactful presence.

In formulating a starting strategy for the RSE affinity group within an organization, affinity group organizers can delineate a short-term plan aimed at establishing a solid foundation and getting started with community engagement. It may be helpful to assemble a dedicated team committed to investing time in initiating activities if group size permits. Note that in the previous sections of this guide we outlined what activities an individual can carry out to build allies, build relationships, etc. At the time, those activities were primarily considered from an individual perspective with an eventual goal of *building* an RSE affinity group. That said, these and similar activities can be carried out under the RSE affinity group umbrella with the new goal of *nurturing* and *sustaining* the RSE affinity group. The success of the short-term plan relies on cultivating an enthusiastic group capable of generating and sustaining momentum within the initial stages.

Looking beyond establishment, the group should develop a long-term plan, spanning a 3 to 5-year horizon, ideally within the same context as developing the establishment strategies. Having a long-term strategy becomes imperative for the sustained growth of the RSE affinity group. The focus here should extend beyond immediate activities, contemplating how to keep the community consistently involved and engaged. Establishing a pathway for members to transition into affinity group leadership roles is integral, ensuring a continuous influx of fresh perspectives resulting in sustained organizational vibrancy and a sense of ownership. Long-term goals may encompass expanding the affinity group's influence across the organization, potentially integrating it with other entities working within the same area and domain. By envisioning a strategic trajectory, the long-term plan serves as a roadmap for the affinity group's evolution, fostering enduring engagement and impact within the organization over the years to come.

6. The Future Path: Navigating What Comes Next

Once a RSE affinity group successfully initiates short-term goals and has charted a long-term strategy, the future trajectory opens up to myriad possibilities, and organizers find themselves at a crossroads of strategic decisions.

As the affinity group and its members gain recognition for their achievements and progress on near-term goals, periodic reflections become important. These reflections serve as a compass for organizers to navigate potential routes ahead. While charting the course, it is essential to carefully evaluate each path, ensuring alignment with organizational objectives and avoiding overextension that could strain the affinity group's capabilities. By considering these different paths, the RSE affinity group can plan for the future and keep growing in a way that makes a real impact.

Securing sources of financial support

Establishing and securing funding for a RSE affinity group within an organization demands a strategic approach that recognizes the diversity of organizational models and potential challenges in obtaining financial support. While some affinity groups may operate with minimal or no funding, having a dedicated financial source can unlock additional opportunities for RSEs within the organization. The choice of a funding model depends on the organization's structure, priorities, and existing sources of support. Some organizations may have precedents, such as societies or clubs, successfully securing funding for their activities, offering inspiration for the RSE affinity group. In cases where securing funding proves challenging, especially in organizations with well-established communities, the affinity group's success and vitality can serve as a persuasive case for expansion.

Exploring informal/formal partnerships with organizational stakeholders who share similar interests, writing proposals/grant requests that promote research while advocating for RSEs, and working with organizational leadership to acknowledge and become vested in the affinity group, may also work to enhance financial support. The funds obtained can be reinvested to support various RSE activities or expand community outreach, potentially extending the affinity group's influence from a single organization to multiple entities within the same sector and domain. Although the funding landscape may be tricky and may vary, the success of a RSE affinity group lies in its adaptability and strategic utilization of available resources to sustain and enhance its impact.

Sustaining interest and engagement

Sustaining interest and engagement within a RSE affinity group in an organization involves a multifaceted approach, where both the affinity group community and leaders collaborate to foster a vibrant and committed community. Active member participation in goal-setting sessions remains important in this regard, ensuring that objectives are not only inspiring but also aligned with the affinity group's changing capabilities. Providing a diverse range of activities contributes to the creation of an inclusive environment, catering to a broad spectrum of interests, which will help the group sustain itself over time.

Recognizing and appreciating volunteer contributions through awards and public acknowledgment becomes integral in reinforcing a collective sense of purpose and commitment. Crucially, leaders must act as facilitators in conflict resolution, establishing open communication and mediation resources to address internal conflicts constructively, ensuring a harmonious collaborative environment. If membership is not able to constructively address disagreements or problematic behavior, members will leave and the group will struggle to meet its goals.

As part of the affinity group's focus, building a sense of community among RSEs within the organization takes center stage. Recognizing that the RSE experience at the core of knowledge is consistent, despite potential variations in execution environments across departments, is crucial. By integrating these aspects into the affinity group's initiatives, it can effectively nurture a cohesive and supportive community, fostering both personal and professional development among its members.

7. Final thoughts: Charting the Course

This brief guide has been your compass, offering insights on research, community building, and navigating the terrain of recognition and funding. As you embark on this journey, flexibility is your friend – adjust, experiment, and let your affinity group evolve.

The path to a thriving RSE affinity group involves continual learning, experimentation, and collaboration. Whether it's securing recognition, building a dedicated team, or securing financial support, each step contributes to the resilience and impact of your affinity group. From short-term plans to long-term visions, the key is to keep it practical. Balance your ambitions with the resources you have. Beyond the practical steps, the essence of a successful RSE affinity group lies in the commitment of its community and

the leadership's ability to foster engagement, sustain interest short-term, building a sense of community, and planning for the long term.

As you look ahead, envision a future where your RSE affinity group becomes a catalyst for collaboration, innovation, and professional growth. The potential is vast, and the impact can be profound. Continue to adapt, learn, and collaborate, for you are not just establishing an affinity group – you are cultivating a dynamic and impactful community that will shape the future of Research Software Engineering within your organization.
